

**Environmental Samples across the National Landscape:
the Scale and Scope of Environmental Sample Collection to Support US-based Research
and Monitoring (2020-2030)**

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This report is derived from surveys conducted in 2020 and 2021 by the Smithsonian Institution's National Museum of Natural History (NMNH) Environmental Working Group*.

Summary of Results

Federal agencies and other United States-based research programs have been rapidly adopting and implementing research and monitoring programs that use environmental samples (envSamples) for sampling ecosystems as a means to address critical scientific and societal issues related to biodiversity, including food security and economics, impacts of climate change, invasive species, the loss of biological diversity, and ecosystem assessment and monitoring. In order to assess the scope and extent of envSample activities in the United States, a June 2020 survey was initiated and conducted by the Environmental Collections Working Group at the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (NMNH). Based on the results of the 2020 survey, a second follow up survey was conducted in July 2021 to refine and better characterize the national landscape. These surveys were conducted in order to prepare a strategy, budget, and requirements for potentially establishing a national repository that would be responsible for cataloging, storing, inventorying, maintaining, conserving, and managing loans of eSamples. For this work, envSamples are defined as collections from an environment that contain evidence of multiple species, which cannot be sorted into individuals. Thus, individual species in an environmental sample cannot be detected and reported without additional investigation. Environmental DNA (envDNA) refers to DNA isolated from an environmental sample.

Respondents were polled to represent the broadest contingent within their agency or programmatic workspace and to reduce overlap of reporting data. We recognize that the respondents and results are a subset of the national enterprise. However, we did attempt to cast the broadest net in order to include a reasonable representation of varieties, scales and approaches to utilizing envSamples. The number of respondents to the two surveys were 83 and 78, respectively for the June 2020 and July 2021 surveys. In each survey, the organizations with the largest number of respondents were NOAA (30 and 21) and Smithsonian (17 and 18). Other Federal organizations included NPS, USDA, USFWS, USGS, US Army, US Navy, and EPA. Respondents also represented state agencies, private research organizations (e.g., WHOI, MBARI), universities and tribal representatives (Figs. 1-2).

Figure 1. Breakdown of respondents to the NMNH Environmental Working Group survey conducted in June of 2020.

Figure 2. Breakdown of respondents to the NMNH Environmental Working Group survey conducted in July of 2021.

The main finding from the initial survey in June 2020 was that there will be significant growth in environmental sampling activities by 2030. At the time of the initial survey, respondents who had already begun to engage in envSample activities had accumulated samples that numbered in the 10s to 100s, with a small portion of respondents having accumulated 1000s of samples. By 2030, a majority of respondents indicated that they expected to have accumulated 1000s of samples or 10,000s (n=22) (Fig. 3). While the respondents were asked for ballpark estimates,

results clearly indicated that 100s of thousands of envSamples would be accumulated by US-based enterprises by 2030 (Fig. 3). By the end of the decade, environmental sampling will have grown by two orders of magnitude.

Figure 3. Rapid growth in sampling of environmental samples is predicted, based on the NMNH Environmental Working Group survey conducted in June of 2020.

The initial survey conducted in June, 2020 indicated that environmental samples were diverse in type. While filtered water samples were the most common type of sample, gut contents, plankton tows, settlement plates, soil, sediment, filtered air, mucus and still other sample-types were targeted as environmental samples (Fig. 4). Similarly, environmental samples were being collected for a variety of reasons, from studies that targeted specific taxa to those that aimed to characterize entire biological communities (Fig. 5).

Figure 4. Environmental samples are diverse in type, based on the NMNH Environmental Working Group survey conducted in June of 2020.

Figure 5. Environmental samples are used in a variety of ways, based on the NMNH Environmental Working Group survey conducted in June of 2020.

The second survey, conducted in July of 2021 was aimed at refining and extending information gathered in the initial survey. This second survey reiterated basic findings from the initial survey, specifically 1) that NOAA and Smithsonian are heavily engaged in envSample collection and that they will rapidly increase the numbers of samples being collected over a 10-year timeframe (100s of thousands), 2) that sources of environmental samples are diverse, 3) and that envSamples are targeted for various aims (i.e., they have high utility). The second survey gathered additional information about re-use of eSamples and eDNA, finding that re-use of samples is already happening. For instance, 46% of respondents indicated that they had gone back to an existing envSample to process or subsample a portion of it for the same purpose it was originally collected, and 34% had gone back to an existing envSample to use it for a purpose other than the one for which it was originally collected. These values increased to 58% and 49%, respectively, for re-use of eDNA for the initial intended purpose or new purpose. This second survey also sought to clarify current practices in collections management for eSamples and eDNA. Only half of respondents (52%) indicated that they had a collections management plan for environmental samples, with a similar response to whether a data management plan was in place (48%). A majority (66%) of respondents indicated a shortfall in funding to efficiently and responsibly manage existing and future envSample and envDNA collections.

Overall, the results of the two surveys indicate that the US will engage heavily in the use of envSamples and envDNA to address a variety of societally relevant issues in the very near future (next 10 years). These activities will result in the accumulation of hundreds of thousands of such samples. While roughly half of respondents had collections and data management plans

in place related to environmental samples, roughly 2/3rds of respondents indicated that they had insufficient funds to responsibly manage these collections. This shortfall in funding compromises the long term utility of environmental samples.

Environmental samples and envDNA are unrepeatable snapshots of ecological communities. While the original goal of the sampling program drives the initial collection and analytical workflow, these same samples can be interrogated for a multitude of uses by other researcher groups. For example, envSamples collected to assess the diversity of fish communities could later be used to look at microbial communities, or envSamples used to collect baseline community knowledge could be later analyzed to search for the presence of a particular species of interest (protected, invasive, etc.). Thus, archiving envSamples provides opportunities to maximize outcomes from the effort, time and knowledge that went into collecting them. Other benefits of archiving envSamples or envDNA derivatives include the facilitation of replicability of important scientific findings. By maintaining and managing samples upon which scientific findings are based, archive collections provide critical access to primary sources of information (the actual material samples) so that other researchers can assess and advance earlier scientific findings. While applications utilizing envDNA have rapidly advanced, it is important to recognize that the field is still in its early stages. We should expect technological advances and the rapid accumulation of new knowledge that will guide future work of importance to ecologists and managers of biological resources that can be conducted on existing and accumulating collections.

Archiving envSamples and envDNA has significant value because they represent biological communities at verified points in time and space. Thus, archiving these samples is vital for addressing critical scientific and societal issues related to biodiversity, including food security and economics, impacts of climate change, invasive species, and the loss of biological diversity, as new knowledge and technologies emerge.

Associated Files:

- 2020 survey summary (eSample Survey-1_Data_All_200618.pdf)
- 2021 survey summary (eSample Survey-2_Data_All_210816_not complete.pdf)
- Anonymized and annotated results for survey conducted in June 2020 (eSAMPLE_Survey1_Annotated_Anon.xlsx)
- Anonymized and annotated results for survey conducted in July 2021 (eSAMPLE_Survey2_Annotated_Anon.xlsx)

Acronyms:

- **NMNH:** National Museum of Natural History
- **SI:** Smithsonian Institution
- **NOAA:** National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
- **NPS:** National Parks Service
- **USDA:** United States Department of Agriculture
- **USFWS:** United State Fish and Wildlife Service

- **USGS:** United States Geological Survey
- **EPA:** Environmental Protection Agency
- **WHOI:** Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute
- **MBARI:** Monterey Bay Research Institute

Definitions

- **Environmental Sample (envSample):** A sample that contains evidence of multiple species that cannot be sorted into individuals. Thus, individual species in an environmental sample cannot be detected and reported without additional investigation.
- **Environmental DNA (envDNA):** DNA isolated from an environmental sample. In principle, this contrasts with genomic DNA, which is extracted directly from an individual specimen, but genomic DNA extracts also may contain the DNA from multiple organisms (for instance, organisms living in association).
- **eDNA:** We reserve the term eDNA to apply to the practice and derived samples from filtering water or air for biomolecular marker analyses. Instead of a slurry or blend of autochthonous biomaterials, eDNA investigates allochthonous as well as autochthonous signal in a sample. While both sample types (slurries vs. filters) contain fractions of targeted and shed products, the relative proportion shed portion is of principal concern in eDNA. Thus, aspects of fate and transport are more relevant in eDNA studies. By this definition, eDNA is a subset of envDNA.

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